

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 78

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 78

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 78:0 A †Maskil of Asaph.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 78:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">מִשְׁכִּיל לְאַסָּף</p>
<p>Psa. 78:1 †Listen, O my people, to my ¹instruction; ^bIncline your ears to the words of my mouth. ² I will ^aopen my mouth in a parable; I will utter ^bdark sayings of old, ³ Which we have heard and known, And ^aour fathers have told us. ⁴ We will ^anot conceal them from their children, But ^btell to the generation to come the praises of the LORD, And His strength and His ^cwondrous works that He has done.</p>	<p>הֶאֱזִינָה עַמִּי תוֹרַתִּי הַטּוֹ אֲזַנְכֶם לְאִמְרֵי־פִי : ² אֶפְתָּחָה בְּמִשְׁלַל פִּי אֲבִיעָה חִידוֹת מִנִּי־קִדְמָה : ³ אֲשֶׁר שָׁמְעֵנוּ וַנִּדְרְעֵם וְאֲבוֹתֵינוּ סִפְרוּ־לָנוּ : ⁴ לֹא נִכְחֹד מִבְּנֵיהֶם לְדוֹר אַחֲרוֹן מִסִּפְרִים תְּהַלְלוֹת יְהוָה וְעִזּוֹנוֹ וְנִפְלְאוֹתָיו אֲשֶׁר עָשָׂה : ⁵ וַיִּקֶּם עֲדוּת בִּיעֲקֹב וְתוֹרָה שָׁם בִּישְׂרָאֵל אֲשֶׁר צִוָּה אֶת־אֲבוֹתֵינוּ לְהוֹדִיעֵם לְבְנֵיהֶם : ⁶ לְמַעַן יֵדְעוּ וַדּוֹר אַחֲרוֹן בְּנִים יִזְכְּרוּ יִקְמוּ וַיִּסְפְּרוּ לְבְנֵיהֶם : ⁷ וַיִּשְׁיִמוּ בְּאֱלֹהִים כְּסֶלֶם וְלֹא יִשְׁכַּחוּ מִעֲלֵלֵי־ אֱלֹהִים וּמִצֹּתָיו יִנְצְרוּ : ⁸ וְלֹא יִהְיוּ אֶפְאֹתָם דּוֹר סוֹרֵר</p>
<p>Psa. 78:5 For He established a ^atestimony in Jacob And appointed a ^blaw in Israel, Which He ^ccommanded our fathers That they should ^{1d}teach them to their children, ⁶ †That the generation to come might know, <i>even</i> ^bthe children <i>yet</i> to be born, <i>That</i> they may arise and ^ctell <i>them</i> to their children, ⁷ That they should put their confidence in God And ^anot forget the works of God, But ^bkeep His commandments, ⁸ And ^anot be like their fathers,</p>	

A ^bstubborn and rebellious generation,
A generation that 'did not
¹prepare its heart
And whose spirit was not ^dfaithful
to God.

Psa. 78:9 The sons of Ephraim ¹were
^aarchers equipped with bows,
Yet ^bthey turned back in the day of
battle.

¹⁰ They ^adid not keep the covenant
of God

And refused to ^bwalk in His law;

¹¹ They ^aforgot His deeds

And His ¹miracles that He had

shown them.

¹² ^aHe wrought wonders before their
fathers

In the land of Egypt, in the ^bfield
of Zoan.

¹³ He ^adivided the sea and caused
them to pass through,

And He made the waters stand

^bup like a heap.

¹⁴ Then He led them with the cloud
by ^aday

And all the night with a ^blight of

fire.

¹⁵ He ^asplit the rocks in the
wilderness

And gave *them* abundant drink like
the ocean depths.

¹⁶ He ^abrought forth streams also
from the rock

And caused waters to run down
like rivers.

Psa. 78:17 Yet they still continued to
sin against Him,

וּמִרְהָרָה דָּוָר לֹא־הִכִּין לְבוֹ
וְלֹא־נִאֲמְנָה אֶת־אֵל רֹחֵהוּ : 9
בְּנֵי־אֶפְרַיִם נוֹשְׁקֵי רוּמֵי־
קִשְׁתָּהּ הִפְכוּ בַיּוֹם קָרָב : 10
לֹא שָׁמְרוּ בְרִית אֱלֹהִים
וּבַתּוֹרָתוֹ מֵאֲנוּ לָלַכְתָּ : 11
וַיִּשְׁכְּחוּ עֲלִילוֹתָיו
וַנִּבְלֵאוֹתָיו אֲשֶׁר הִרְאָם : 12
נִגְדוּ אֲבוֹתָם עֲשָׂה כִּלְאֵי
בְּאֶרֶץ מִצְרַיִם שְׂדֵה־צֹעַן : 13
בִּקְעֵי יַם וַיַּעֲבִירֵם וַיַּצַּב־מַיִם
כְּמוֹ־נָד : 14 וַיִּנְחֵם כְּעָנָן
יוֹמָם וְכָל־הַלַּיְלָה בְּאוֹר
אֵשׁ : 15 יִבְקַע צַרִּים בַּמִּדְבָּר
וַיִּשְׁקֵם כַּתְּהֻמוֹת רַבָּה : 16
וַיּוֹצֵא נוֹזְלִים מִסֶּלַע וַיִּזְרַד
כַּנְּהַרּוֹת מַיִם : 17 וַיּוֹסִיפוּ
עוֹד לַחֲטֹא־לוֹ לַמְּרוֹת
עַל־יוֹן בַּצִּיָּה : 18 וַיִּנְסוּ־אֶל
בְּלִבָּם לִשְׁאֵל־אֶכְל
לְנַפְשָׁם : 19 וַיִּדְבְּרוּ בְּאֱלֹהִים
אָמְרוּ הֲתִיכֹל אֵל לַעֲרֹךְ
שְׁלִחָן בַּמִּדְבָּר : 20 הֲתֵן הַכֶּהֱ-

To ^arebel against the Most High in the desert.

¹⁸ And in their heart they ^aput God to the test

By asking ^bfood according to their desire.

¹⁹ Then they spoke against God; They said, "Can God prepare a table in the wilderness?

²⁰ "Behold, He ^astruck the rock so that waters gushed out,

And streams were overflowing;

Can He give bread also?

Will He provide ^{1b}meat for His people?"

Psa. 78:21 Therefore the LORD heard and ¹was ^afull of wrath;

And a fire was kindled against Jacob

And anger also mounted against Israel,

²² Because they ^adid not believe in God

And did not trust in His salvation.

²³ Yet He commanded the clouds above

And ^aopened the doors of heaven;

²⁴ He ^arained down manna upon them to eat

And gave them ^{1b}food from heaven.

²⁵ Man did eat the bread of ¹angels; He sent them ²food ^{3a}in

abundance.

²⁶ He ^acaused the east wind to blow in the heavens

And by His ¹power He directed the south wind.

²⁷ When He rained ¹meat upon them like the dust,

צֹר וַיִּזְזוּבוּ מֵיָמִים וַיִּנְחָלִים

לְשֹׁטְפוֹ הַגֵּם-לָהֶם יוּכַל יְהוָה

אִם-יִכְיֶין שְׂאֵר לְעַמּוֹ : ²¹ לָכֵן

אִשְׁמַע יְהוָה וַיִּתְעַבֵּר וְאִשׁ

נִשְׁקָה בִּיעֲקֹב וְגַם-אֶף עָלָה

בִּישְׂרָאֵל : ²² כִּי לֹא הֶאֱמִינוּ

בְּאֱלֹהִים וְלֹא בָטְחוּ

בִּישׁוּעָתוֹ : ²³ וַיִּצְוּ שְׁחָקִים

מִמַּעַל וַדְּלִתִּי שָׁמַיִם פִּתְחָת :

²⁴ וַיִּמְטֵר עֲלֵיהֶם מִן הַשָּׁמַיִם לֶאֱכֹל

וַדְּגַן-שָׁמַיִם נָתַן לָמוֹ : ²⁵

לָחֶם אַבִּירִים אָכַל אִישׁ

צִידָה שָׁלַח לָהֶם לְשִׁבְעָ : ²⁶

יֶסַע קָדִים בְּשָׁמַיִם וַיִּנְהַג

בְּעֵזוֹ תִימֵן : ²⁷ וַיִּמְטֵר

עֲלֵיהֶם כֶּעֶפֶר שְׂאֵר וְכִחֹל

זָמִים עֹף כִּנֹּף : ²⁸ וַיִּפֹּל

בְּקֶרֶב מִחֲנֹהוּ סָבִיב

לְמִשְׁכְּנֹתָיו : ²⁹ וַיֹּאכְלוּ

וַיִּשְׂבְּעוּ מְאֹד וְתֹאֲתָם יָבֵא

לָהֶם : ³⁰ לֹא-זָרוּ מִתֹּאֲתָם

עוֹד אָכְלָם בְּפִיהֶם : ³¹ וְאֶף

אֱלֹהִים אֲעֲלֶה בָהֶם וַיִּהְיֶה

Even ^awinged fowl like the sand
of the seas,
28 Then He let *them* fall in the midst
of ¹their camp,
Round about their dwellings.
29 So they ^aate and were well filled,
And their desire He gave to them.
30 ¹Before they had satisfied their
desire,
^aWhile their food was in their
mouths,
31 The ^aanger of God rose against
them
And killed ¹some of their ^bstoutest
ones,
And ²subdued the choice men of
Israel.
32 In spite of all this they ^astill sinned
And ^bdid not believe in His
wonderful works.
33 So He brought ^atheir days to an
end in ¹futility
And their years in sudden terror.

Psa. 78:34 When He killed
them, then they ^asought Him,
And returned and searched
^bdiligently for God;
35 And they remembered that God
was their ^arock,
And the Most High God their
^bRedeemer.
36 But they ^adeceived Him with their
mouth
And ^blied to Him with their
tongue.
37 For their heart was not ^asteadfast
toward Him,
Nor were they faithful in His
covenant.

בְּמִשְׁמַנֵּיהֶם וּבַחֹרֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל
הִכְרִיעַ : 32 בְּכֹל־זֹאת
חֲטְאוּ-עוֹד וְלֹא־הֶאֱמִינוּ
בְּנִפְלְאוֹתָיו : 33 וַיִּכַּל־בַּהֶבֶל
יְמֵיהֶם וַשְּׂנוֹתָם בַּבְּהִלָּה : 34
אִם־הִרְגָם וּדְרֹשׁוּהוּ וְשׁוּבוּ
וּשְׁחֲרוּ־אֵל : 35 וַיִּזְכְּרוּ כִי־
אֱלֹהִים צוּרִם וְאֵל עֲלִיּוֹן
גֹּאֲלָם : 36 וַיִּפְתּוּהוּ בְּפִיהֶם
וּבִלְשׁוֹנָם יִכְזְבוּ־לוֹ : 37 וְלִבָּם
לֹא־נָכוֹן עֲמּוֹ וְלֹא נֶאֱמְנוּ
בְּבְרִיתוֹ : 38 וְהוּא רַחוּם |
יִכַּפֵּר עוֹן וְלֹא־יִשְׁתִּית
וְהִרְבָּה לְהִשָּׁיב אִפּוֹ וְלֹא־
יַעִיר כָּל־חַמָּתוֹ : 39 וַיִּזְכֹּר
כִּי־בֶשֶׂר הִמָּה רוּחַ הוֹלֵךְ
וְלֹא יִשׁוּב : 40 כַּמָּה יִמְרוּהוּ
בַמִּדְבָּר יַעֲצִיבוּהוּ בִישִׁמּוֹן :
41 וַיִּשׁוּבוּ וַיִּנְסוּ אֵל וּקְדוֹשׁ
יִשְׂרָאֵל הִתּוֹו : 42 לֹא־זָכְרוּ
אֶת־יְדוֹ הַיּוֹם אֲשֶׁר־פָּדָם מִנִּי־
צָר : 43 אֲשֶׁר־שָׂם בְּמִצְרַיִם
אֶת־וֹתָיו וַיִּמּוּפְתּוּ בַשְּׂדֵה־

38 But He, being ^acompassionate,
^{1b}forgave *their* iniquity and did not
destroy *them*;
And often He ^{2c}restrained His
anger
And did not arouse all His wrath.
39 Thus ^aHe remembered that they
were but ^bflesh,
A ^{1c}wind that passes and does not
return.

Psa. 78:40 How often they
^arebelled against Him in the wilderness
And ^bgrieved Him in the ^cdesert!
41 Again and again they ^{1a}tempted
God,
And pained the ^bHoly One of
Israel.
42 They ^adid not remember ^bHis
¹power,
The day when He ^credeemed them
from the adversary,
43 When He performed His ^asigns in
Egypt
And His ^bmarvels in the field of
Zoan,
44 And ^aturned their rivers to blood,
And their streams, they could not
drink.
45 He sent among them swarms of
^aflies which devoured them,
And ^bfrogs which destroyed them.
46 He gave also their crops to the
^agrasshopper
And the product of their labor to
the ^blocust.
47 He ¹destroyed their vines with
^ahailstones
And their sycamore trees with
frost.

צָעַן : 44 וַיִּהְיֶה לָדָם יְאֲרִיָּהֶם
וְנִזְלִיָּהֶם כָּל־יִשְׁתַּיִּיזִן : 45
יִשְׁלַח בָּהֶם עֲרָב וַיֹּאכְלֵם
וַצְּפִירֵי־עַ וַתִּשְׁחִיתֵם : 46 וַיִּתֵּן
לַחֲסִיל יְבוּלִם וַיִּגְיַעֵם
לְאַרְבֶּה : 47 יַהֲלֹג בַּבְּרָד
גִּבְנֵם וְשִׁקְמוֹתֵם בַּחֲנַמִּל : 48
וַיִּסְגֵּר לַבְּרָד בְּעִירָם
וּמִקְנֵיהֶם לְרִשְׁפִּים : 49
יִשְׁלַח־בָּם אֶחָדֹן אַפֹּי עֲבָרָה
וּזְעֵם וְצָרָה מִשְׁלַחַת מִלְּאֲכֵי
רָעִים : 50 יִפְלֹס נְתִיב לְאַפֹּי
לְא־חֲשׂוֹךְ מִמְּוֹת נַפְשָׁם
וְחִיתָם לְדַבֵּר הַסִּגִּיר : 51 וַיִּיָּךְ
כָּל־בְּכוֹר בְּמִצְרַיִם רְאֵשִׁית
אוֹזְנִים בְּאֶהֱלֵי־חָם : 52 וַיִּסַּע
כִּצְאוֹן עִמּוֹ וַיִּנְהֲגֵם כְּעֶדֶד
בַּמִּדְבָּר : 53 וַיִּנְחֵם לְבַשְׁת
וְלֹא פָתְחוּ וְאֶת־אוֹיְבֵיהֶם
כִּסְתָה תֵימִם : 54 וַיִּבִיֵּאֵם אֶל־
גְּבוּל קְדָשׁוֹ הַר־זֵה קָנְתָה
יְמִינוֹ : 55 וַיִּגְרֹשׁ מִפְּנֵיהֶם א
גוֹיִם וַיִּפְּלֵם בְּחֶבֶל נִתְלָה

⁴⁸ He gave over their ^acattle also to the hailstones

And their herds to bolts of lightning.

⁴⁹ He ^asent upon them His burning anger,

Fury and indignation and trouble,
¹A band of destroying angels.

⁵⁰ He leveled a path for His anger;
He did not spare their soul from death,

But ^agave over their life to the plague,

⁵¹ And ^asmote all the firstborn in Egypt,

The ^bfirst *issue* of their virility in the tents of ^cHam.

⁵² But He ^aled forth His own people like sheep

And guided them in the wilderness ^blike a flock;

⁵³ He led them ^asafely, so that they did not fear;

But ^bthe sea engulfed their enemies.

Psa. 78:54 So ^aHe brought them to His holy ¹land,

To this ^{2b}hill country ^cwhich His right hand had gained.

⁵⁵ He also ^adrove out the nations before them

And ^bapportioned them for an inheritance by measurement,

And made the tribes of Israel dwell in their tents.

⁵⁶ Yet they ^{1a}tempted and ^brebelled against the Most High God

And did not keep His testimonies,

⁵⁷ But turned back and ^aacted treacherously like their fathers;

וַיִּשְׁכַּן בְּאַהֲלֵיהֶם שְׁבִטֵי

יִשְׂרָאֵל : ⁵⁶ וַיִּנְסוּ וַיִּמְרוּ אֶת-

אֱלֹהֵיהֶם עַל־יּוֹן אֲעֲדוּתָיו לֹא

שָׁמְרוּ : ⁵⁷ וַיִּסְגּוּ וַיִּבְגְּדוּ

כַּאֲבוֹתָם נְהַפְּכוּ כַּקֶּשֶׁת

רַמְיָהּ : ⁵⁸ וַיִּכְעִיסוּהוּ

בְּבִמּוֹתָם וּבְפִסִּילֵיהֶם

וַיִּקְנִיאוּהוּ : ⁵⁹ שָׁמַע אֱלֹהִים

וַיִּתְעַבֵּר וַיִּמְאַס מְאֹד

בְּיִשְׂרָאֵל : ⁶⁰ וַיִּטַּשׁ מִשְׁכַּן

שְׁלוֹ אֱהֵל שֹׁכֵן בְּאֶרֶם : ⁶¹

וַיִּתֵּן לַשִּׁבְי עֵזוֹ וַתִּפְאֲרֵתוּ

בְּיַד-צָר : ⁶² וַיִּסְגַּר לַחֲרָב

עַמּוֹ וּבִנְחָלָתוֹ הִתְעַבֵּר : ⁶³

בַּחֲזֵרָיו אֲכָלָה-אֵשׁ

וּבְתוֹלָתָיו לֹא הוֹלִלּוּ : ⁶⁴

כַּהֲנִיּוֹ בַּחֲרָב נִפְלוּ

וְאֵל־מִנְתָּיו לֹא תִבְכֶּינָה : ⁶⁵

וַיִּקַּץ כִּישָׁן וְאֶדְנִי כְּגִבּוֹר

מִתְרוֹנֵן מִיַּיִן : ⁶⁶ וַיִּד-צָרָיו

אֲחֹר חֲרַפְתָּ עוֹלָם נָתַן

לָמוֹ : ⁶⁷ וַיִּמְאַס בְּאַהֲלֵי יוֹסֵף

וּבְשֵׁבֶט אֲפֹרִים לֹא בָחַר : ⁶⁸

They ^bturned aside like a treacherous bow.

⁵⁸ For they ^aprovoked Him with their ^bhigh places

And ^caroused His jealousy with their ^dgraven images.

⁵⁹ When God heard, He ¹was filled with ^awrath

And greatly ^babhorred Israel;

⁶⁰ So that He ^aabandoned the ^bdwelling place at Shiloh,

The tent ¹which He had pitched among men,

⁶¹ And gave up His ^astrength to captivity

And His glory ^binto the hand of the adversary.

⁶² He also ^adelivered His people to the sword,

And ¹was filled with wrath at His inheritance.

⁶³ ^aFire devoured ¹His young men, And ¹His ^bvirgins had no wedding songs.

⁶⁴ ¹His ^apriests fell by the sword, And ¹His ^bwidows could not weep.

Psa. 78:65 Then the Lord ^aawoke as *if from* sleep, Like a ^bwarrior ¹overcome by wine.

⁶⁶ He ^{1a}drove His adversaries backward;

He put on them an everlasting reproach.

⁶⁷ He also ^arejected the tent of Joseph,

And did not choose the tribe of Ephraim,

⁶⁸ But chose the tribe of Judah,

וַיִּבְחַר אֶת־שֵׁבֶט יְהוּדָה
אֶת־הַר צִיּוֹן אֲשֶׁר אָהֵב : ⁶⁹
וַיִּבֶן כְּמוֹ־רַמִּים מִקִּדְּשׁוֹ
כְּאֶרֶץ יִסְדָּה לְעוֹלָם : ⁷⁰
וַיִּבְחַר בְּדָוִד עַבְדּוֹ וַיִּקְחֵהוּ
מִמְּכֹלֵאת צָאן : ⁷¹ מֵאֶתֶר
עָלוֹת הֵבִיאוּ לְרַעוֹת בְּיַעֲקֹב
עַמּוֹ וּבְיִשְׂרָאֵל נִחְלָתוּ : ⁷²
וַיִּרְעַם כֹּתֶם לְבָבוֹ וּבִתְבוּנֹת
כַּפָּיו יִנְחָם :

<p>Mount ^aZion which He loved. 69 And He ^abuilt His sanctuary like the heights, Like the earth which He has founded forever. 70 He also ^achose David His servant And took him from the sheepfolds; 71 From ^{1a}the care of the ²ewes ^bwith suckling lambs He brought him To ^cshepherd Jacob His people, And Israel ^dHis inheritance. 72 So he shepherded them according to the ^aintegrity of his heart, And guided them with his skillful hands.</p>	
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References

Psalm 78:0

†Possibly, *Contemplative*, or *Didactic*, or *Skillful Psalm*

Psalm 78:1

¹Or *law, teaching*

^aIs 51:4

^bIs 55:3

Psalm 78:2

^aPs 49:4; Matt 13:35

^bProv 1:6

Psalm 78:3

^aPs 44:1

Psalm 78:4

^aEx 12:26; Deut 6:7; 11:19; Job 15:18; Ps 145:4; Is 38:19; Joel 1:3

^bEx 13:8, 14; Ps 22:30

^cJob 37:16; Ps 26:7; 71:17

Psalm 78:5

¹Lit *make them known*

^aPs 19:7; 81:5; Is 8:20

^bPs 147:19

^cDeut 6:4-9

^dDeut 4:9

Psalm 78:6

^aPs 102:18

^bPs 22:31

^cDeut 11:19

Psalm 78:7

^aDeut 4:9; 6:12; 8:14

^bDeut 4:2; 5:1, 29; 27:1; Josh 22:5

Psalm 78:8

¹Or *put right*

^a2 Kin 17:14; 2 Chr 30:7; Ezek 20:18

^bEx 32:9; Deut 9:7, 24; 31:27; Judg 2:19; Is 30:9
^cJob 11:13; Ps 78:37
^aPs 51:10

Psalm 78:9

¹Or *being*
^a1 Chr 12:2
^bJudg 20:39; Ps 78:57

Psalm 78:10

^aJudg 2:20; 1 Kin 11:11; 2 Kin 17:15; 18:12
^bPs 119:1; Jer 32:23; 44:10, 23

Psalm 78:11

¹Or *wonderful works*
^aPs 106:13

Psalm 78:12

^aEx chs 7-12; Ps 106:22
^bNum 13:22; Ps 78:43; Is 19:11; 30:4; Ezek 30:14

Psalm 78:13

^aEx 14:21; Ps 74:13; 136:13
^bEx 15:8; Ps 33:7

Psalm 78:14

^aEx 13:21; Ps 105:39
^bEx 14:24

Psalm 78:15

^aEx 17:6; Num 20:11; Ps 105:41; 114:8; Is 48:21; 1 Cor 10:4

Psalm 78:16

^aNum 20:8, 10, 11

Psalm 78:17

^aDeut 9:22; Is 63:10; Heb 3:16

Psalm 78:18

^aEx 17:6; Deut 6:16; Ps 78:41, 56; 95:9; 106:14; 1 Cor 10:9
^bNum 11:4

Psalm 78:19

^aEx 16:3; Num 11:4; 20:3; 21:5; Ps 23:5

Psalm 78:20

¹Lit *flesh*

^aNum 20:11; Ps 78:15, 16

^bNum 11:18

Psalm 78:21

¹Or *became infuriated*

^aNum 11:1

Psalm 78:22

^aDeut 1:32; 9:23; Heb 3:18

Psalm 78:23

^aGen 7:11; Mal 3:10

Psalm 78:24

¹Lit *grain*

^aEx 16:4

^bPs 105:40; John 6:31

Psalm 78:25

¹Lit *mighty ones*

²Or *provision*

³Lit *to satiation*

^aEx 16:3

Psalm 78:26

¹Or *strength*

^aNum 11:31

Psalm 78:27

¹Lit *flesh*

^aEx 16:13; Ps 105:40

Psalm 78:28

¹Lit *His*

Psalm 78:29

^aNum 11:19, 20

Psalm 78:30

¹Lit *They were not estranged from*

^aNum 11:33

Psalm 78:31

¹Lit *among their fat ones*

²Lit *caused to bow down*

^aNum 11:33, 34; Job 20:23

^bIs 10:16

Psalm 78:32

^aNum chs 14, 16, 17

^bNum 14:11; Ps 78:11

Psalm 78:33

¹Lit *vanity, a mere breath*

^aNum 14:29, 35

Psalm 78:34

^aNum 21:7; Hos 5:15

^bPs 63:1

Psalm 78:35

^aDeut 32:4

^bEx 15:13; Deut 9:26; Ps 74:2; Is 41:14

Psalm 78:36

^aEx 24:7, 8; Ezek 33:31

^bEx 32:7, 8; Is 57:11

Psalm 78:37

^aPs 51:10; 78:8; Acts 8:21

Psalm 78:38

¹Lit *covered over, atoned for*

²Lit *turned away*

^aEx 34:6

^bNum 14:18-20

Is 48:9

Psalm 78:39

¹Or *breath*

^aJob 10:9; Ps 103:14

^bGen 6:3

Job 7:7, 16; Ps 103:14; James 4:14

Psalm 78:40

^aPs 95:8, 9; 106:43; 107:11; Heb 3:16

^bPs 95:10; Is 63:10; Eph 4:30

Ps 106:14

Psalm 78:41

¹Or *put God to the test*

^aNum 14:22

^b2 Kin 19:22; Ps 89:18

Psalm 78:42

¹Lit *hand*

^aJudg 8:34

^bPs 44:3

Ps 106:10

Psalm 78:43

^aPs 105:27

^bEx 4:21; 7:3

Psalm 78:44

^aEx 7:20; Ps 105:29

Psalm 78:45

^aEx 8:24; Ps 105:31

^bEx 8:6; Ps 105:30

Psalm 78:46

^a1 Kin 8:37; Ps 105:34

^bEx 10:14

Psalm 78:47

¹Lit *was killing*

^aEx 9:23-25; Ps 105:32

Psalm 78:48

^aEx 9:19

Psalm 78:49

¹Lit *A deputation of angels of evil*

^aEx 15:7

Psalm 78:50

^aEx 12:29, 30

Psalm 78:51

^aEx 12:29; Ps 105:36; 135:8; 136:10

^bGen 49:3

^cPs 105:23, 27; 106:22

Psalm 78:52

^aEx 15:22

^bPs 77:20

Psalm 78:53

^aEx 14:19, 20

^bEx 14:27, 28; Ps 106:11

Psalm 78:54

¹Lit *border, territory*

²Or *mountain*

^aEx 15:17

^bPs 68:16; Is 11:9

^cPs 44:3

Psalm 78:55

^aJosh 11:16-23; Ps 44:2

^bJosh 13:7; 23:4; Ps 105:11; 135:12

Psalm 78:56

¹Or *put to the test*

^aPs 78:18

^bJudg 2:11-13; Ps 78:40

Psalm 78:57

^aEzek 20:27, 28

^bHos 7:16

Psalm 78:58

^aDeut 4:25; Judg 2:12; 1 Kin 14:9; Is 65:3

^bLev 26:30; 1 Kin 3:2; 2 Kin 16:4; Jer 17:3

^cDeut 32:16, 21; 1 Kin 14:22

^dEx 20:4; Lev 26:1; Deut 4:25

Psalm 78:59

¹Or *became infuriated*

^aDeut 1:34; 9:19; Ps 106:40

^bLev 26:30; Deut 32:19; Amos 6:8

Psalm 78:60

¹Some ancient versions read *where He dwelt*

^a1 Sam 4:11; Ps 78:67; Jer 7:12, 14; 26:6

^bJosh 18:1

Psalm 78:61

^aPs 63:2; 132:8

^b1 Sam 4:17

Psalm 78:62

¹Or *became infuriated*

^aJudg 20:21; 1 Sam 4:10

Psalm 78:63

¹Or *their*

^aNum 11:1; 21:28; Is 26:11; Jer 48:45

^bJer 7:34; 16:9; Lam 2:21

Psalm 78:64

¹Or *their*

^a1 Sam 4:17; 22:18

^bJob 27:15; Ezek 24:23

Psalm 78:65

¹Or *sobered up from*

^aPs 44:23; 73:20

^bIs 42:13

Psalm 78:66

¹Lit *smote*

^{a1} Sam 5:6

Psalm 78:67

^aPs 78:60

Psalm 78:68

^aPs 87:2; 132:13

Psalm 78:69

^{a1} Kin 6:1-38

Psalm 78:70

^{a1} Sam 16:11, 12

Psalm 78:71

¹Lit *following*

²Lit *ewes which gave suck, He...*

^{a2} Sam 7:8; Is 40:11

^bGen 33:13

^{c2} Sam 5:2; 1 Chr 11:2; Ps 28:9

^{d1} Sam 10:1

Psalm 78:72

^{a1} Kin 9:4

Targum

Psa. 78:1 A teaching of the holy spirit, composed by Asaph. Hear, O my people, my Torah; incline your ears to the utterances of my mouth. ² I will open my mouth in a proverb; I will declare riddles from ancient times. ³ Which we have heard and known, and [which] our fathers told to us. ⁴ We will not hide it from their sons, recounting the psalms of the LORD to a later generation, and his might, and the wonders that he performed. ⁵ And he established a witness among those of the house of Jacob, and he decreed a Torah among those of the house of Israel, which he commanded our fathers to teach to their sons. ⁶ So that [another generation, sons still to be born, should know; they will arise and tell it to their children.] ⁷ And they will place their hope in God, and not forget the works of God, and they will keep his commandments. ⁸ And they will not be like their fathers, a stubborn and vexing generation, a generation whose heart was not firm with its lord, and its spirit was not faithful to God. ⁹ While they were living in Egypt, the sons of Ephraim became arrogant; they calculated the appointed time, and erred; they went out thirty years before the appointed time, with weapons of war, and warriors bearing bows. They turned around and were killed on the day of battle. ¹⁰ Because they did not keep the covenant of God and refused to walk in his Torah. ¹¹ And the people, the house of Israel, forgot his deeds and his wonders that he showed them. ¹² In front of Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, and the tribes of their ancestors, he performed wonders in the land of Egypt, the field of Tanis. ¹³ He split the sea with the staff of Moses their leader, and made them to pass through, and he made the water stand up, fastened like a skin bottle. ¹⁴ And he guided them with the cloud by day, and all of the night with the light of fire. ¹⁵ He split mountains with the staff of Moses their leader in the wilderness; and he gave drink as if from the great deeps. ¹⁶ And he brought forth streams of water from the rock, and he made water come down like flowing rivers. ¹⁷ But they continued still to sin before him, to provoke anger in the presence of the Most High in the dry wilderness. ¹⁸ And they tempted God in their heart, to ask for food for their souls. ¹⁹ And they complained in the presence of the LORD; they said, "Is there the ability in the presence of God to set a table in the wilderness?" ²⁰ Behold, he already has smitten a rock, and water gushed out, and streams flowed; is he also able to give bread, or to arrange food for his people? ²¹ Then it was heard in the presence of God, and he was angry, and fire was made to come up on those of the house of Jacob, and also harsh anger came up on Israel. ²² For they did not believe in God, and did not put their trust in his redemption. ²³ And he commanded the skies above and he opened the windows of heaven. ²⁴ And he made descend on them manna to eat, and he gave them the grain of heaven. ²⁵ The sons of men ate food that came down from the abode of angels; he sent them provisions unto satiety. ²⁶ He made the east wind move in the heavens, and guided the south wind by his strength. ²⁷ And he made flesh descend on them like dust, and flying fowl like the sand of the sea. ²⁸ And he made them fall in the

midst of his camp, round about its tents. ²⁹ And they ate and were very satisfied; so he brought to them their craving. ³⁰ They did not turn from their craving, still their food was in their mouth – ³¹ And the anger of God went up on them, and he slew some of their champions, and he subdued the young men of Israel. ³² For all this they sinned again, and did not believe in his wonders. ³³ And he ended their days with nothingness, and their years with disaster. ³⁴ Whenever he killed them, they sought him, repenting; and they will repent and pray in the presence of God. ³⁵ And they remembered, for God is their strength, and the Most High God is their redeemer. ³⁶ And they enticed him with their mouth, and they lie to him with their tongue. ³⁷ Because their heart was not faithful to him, and they did not believe in his covenant. ³⁸ But he is merciful, atoning for their sins, and does not destroy them; and he frequently turns from his anger, and he will not hasten all his wrath against them. ³⁹ And he remembers that they are sons of flesh, a breath that goes away and does not return. ⁴⁰ How they would rebel against him in the wilderness! They would cause anger in his presence in a desolate place. ⁴¹ And they turned and tempted God, and brought regret to the Holy One of Israel. ⁴² They did not remember his miracle, and the day that he redeemed them from the oppressor. ⁴³ Who set out his signs in Egypt, and his wonders in the field of Tanis. ⁴⁴ And he turned their canals to blood, and they could not drink from their streams. ⁴⁵ He will incite against them a mass of wild animals, and exterminate them; likewise frogs, and he will slaughter them. ⁴⁶ And he gave and handed over their grain to the grasshopper, and their toil to the locust. ⁴⁷ And he stripped their vines with hail, and their sycamores with locusts. ⁴⁸ And he handed over their cattle to the hail, and their flocks to sparks of fire. ⁴⁹ He will incite against them two hundred and fifty plagues in the harshness of his anger, in wrath, and in hostility, and in woe; which are sent in due time by evil messengers. ⁵⁰ He will travel on the path of his harshness, not keeping their soul from death, and handing over their cattle to the plague. ⁵¹ And he slew all the firstborn in Egypt, the beginning of their sorrow in the tents of Ham. ⁵² And he led his people like a flock, and guided them like a sheep flock in the wilderness. ⁵³ And he settled them securely, and they did not fear; and the sea covered their enemies. ⁵⁴ And he brought them into the territory of the site of the Temple, the same mountain that his right hand created. ⁵⁵ And he drove out the Gentiles before them, and settled them in the lot of his inheritance, and settled the tribes of Israel in their tents. ⁵⁶ But they tempted and provoked in the presence of God Most High, and they did not keep his testimony. ⁵⁷ And they relapsed and did evil like their fathers; they became bent like a bow that shoots arrows. ⁵⁸ And they caused anger in his presence with their libations; and they made him jealous with their idols and images. ⁵⁹ It was heard in the presence of God, and he became angry, and his soul was very disgusted with Israel. ⁶⁰ And he abandoned the tabernacle of Shiloh, the tent where his presence did abide among the sons of men. ⁶¹ And he handed over his Torah to captivity, and his splendor to the hand of the oppressor. ⁶² And he handed over his people to those who slay with the sword, and became angry with his inheritance. ⁶³ The fire consumed his young men, and his young

women were not respected. ⁶⁴ His priests will fall with the killing of the sword, and his widows had no time to weep. [ANOTHER TARGUM: At the time when the Philistines captured the ark of the LORD, the priests of Shiloh, Hophni and Phinehas fell by the sword; and at the time when they informed his wives, they did not weep, for they too died on that same day.] ⁶⁵ And the LORD woke up like a sleeper, like a man who opens his eyes from wine. ⁶⁶ And he smote his oppressors on their behinds with hemorrhoids; he gave them eternal disgrace. ⁶⁷ And he was disgusted with the tabernacle spread over the territory of Joseph; and he took no pleasure in the tribe of Ephraim. ⁶⁸ But he was pleased with the tribe of Judah, with Mount Zion that he loves. ⁶⁹ And he built his sanctuary like the horn of the wild ox, fixed like the earth that he founded forever and ever. ⁷⁰ And he was pleased with David his servant, and took him from the flocks of sheep. ⁷¹ And he brought him [away] from [following] after sucklings to rule over Jacob his people, and over Israel his inheritance. ⁷² And he reigned over them in the perfection of his heart, and he will guide them by the understanding of his hands.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Psalmist surveys Israel's history from the time of bondage in Egypt until the reign of King David. This is a span of over four hundred years. The history surveyed is not necessarily in chronological order. The events of these years stem from the LORD, who desired that His Holy Torah should be the supreme authority over Israel. The LORD humbled Israel in Egypt so that they would be ready to accept the Torah at Mount Sinai. The LORD settled the people in the Promised Land as an independent nation. David was anointed the King of Israel. During this period, David met several challenges. The powerful tribe of Ephriam challenged David. They were the descendants of Joseph. They were proud that Joshua ben Nun, the conqueror of the Promised Land, was from their tribe. The Tabernacle and the Ark of the Covenant resided in Shiloh for 369 years. Shiloh was located in Ephriam's territory. Yerevan ben Nevat of Ephriam arose to challenge Solomon, leading to the ten tribes leaving the Kingdom.

Verse two

Asaph believed that he solved the riddle of why the LORD allowed certain events to happen to Israel.

I will open my mouth with a parable; I shall solve riddles from antiquity.

The rest of the Psalm is a recount of history.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

